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PREDNISOLONE INDUCED CUSHING'S SYNDROME IN SEROPOSITIVE INFLAMMATORY ARTHRITIS: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Aim-The main aim of the study is to report the drug related problem occurred in order to prevent its recurrence Case presentation-A 23 year female patient presented with complaint of generalized swelling of body since 8 days, breathlessness since 3 days and fever since 3 days. She is Known case of seropositive inflammatory arthritis since 1 year and taking prednisolone 20 mg b.i.d. Examination-She was having tachycardia, oedema, moon shape face. Lab investigation-her serum cortisol level is elevated and anti CCP antibodies were present hence diagnosed as prednisolone induced cushingoid syndrome with seropositive inflammatory arthritis. Treatment-She was treated with Inj. Furosemide 40 mg IV b.i.d., Neb. Budesonide + Salbutamol every 6 hourly, Tab. Hydroxychloroquine 200 mg PO b.i.d., Tab. Methotrexate 15 mg PO Once a week, Tab. Calcium carbonate 500 mg PO o.d. and other symptomatic treatment. Conclusion-The prednisolone was withdrawn in tapered manner and the patient became normal and discharged.

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INTRODUCTION

Cushing syndrome may be endogenous or exogenous, but clinically it is mainly due to the drugs. Cushing syndrome occurred during the corticosteroid therapy is purely the drug induced disorders. [3, 4] It is one of the widely noticed conditions in several hospitals across the globe which requires prompt medical attention to control its progression and prevent the complications. Drug induced disorders are widely preventable by optimizing the therapeutic regimens for an individual, the main aim of this case report is to enlighten the medical condition and assures the patient safety from drug induced disorders. Cushing syndrome is a condition characterized by high blood levels of cortisol or other exogenous compounds of glucocorticoids. The pathophysiological mechanism differs based on the cause of Cushing syndrome. Prolonged administration of exogenous glucocorticoid hormones are the most common cause of Cushing syndrome. Development of Cushingoid state is infrequent adverse drug reaction of endocrine system due to the use steroids like prednisolone. [5]

AIM:

The main aim of the study is to enlighten the drug related problem and address such problem in order to prevent the occurrence of adverse event & optimizing drug therapy.

CASE PRESENTATION:

A 23 years female patient presented with complaint of generalized swelling of body since 8 days, breathlessness since 3 days and fever (intermittent) since 3 days. She is known case of seropositive inflammatory arthritis since last 1 year and taking prednisolone 20 mg b.i.d. Lab data shows her serum cortisol level was elevated.

PAST MEDICATIONS:

- Tab Indomethacin 50 mg P.O. b.i.d.
- Tab Prednisolone 10 mg P.O. b.i.d.
- Tab Pantoprazole 40 mg P.O. b.i.d.

INVESTIGATIONS:

- Hb-12.2 gm%
- RBC-3.2 million/cumm
- TLC- 6,800 cells/cumm

CONFIRMATORY TEST:

- ✓ RA Factor ^{+ve.}
- ✓ Anti-CCP Antibody 66.65U/ml
- ✓ Serum cortisol-35.9mcg/dl

RA Factor is important marker to diagnose the rheumatoid arthritis condition, Anti citrullinated peptide antibody is supportive test for seropositive conditions for arthritis. Elevated serum cortisol levels are significant to differentially diagnose the Cushingoid condition, which were found to be elevated after the prednisolone administration.

TREATMENT:

1. Inj Furosemide 40 mg I.V. 1-1-0
2. Inj Pantoprazole 40 mg I.V. 1-0-1
3. Budecort + Salbutamol Neb. 6 hrly.
4. Tab. Paracetamol 500 mg P.O. 1-1-1
5. Tab Hydroxychloroquine 200 mg P.O. o.d.
6. Tab Methotrexate 15 mg P.O. once a week
7. Tab prednisolone 5 mg P.O. b.i.d.

As patient was suffering from anasarca (out ruled from obesity) the Furosemide was prescribed to reduce edema, Budecort + Salbutamol were given to treat breathlessness symptomatically, Hydroxychloroquine was prescribed as anti-inflammatory agent at dose of 200mg. Methotrexate was prescribed as conventional chemical Disease-modifying antirheumatic drug to modify the course of inflammatory arthritis and slow the progression.

DISCHARGE MEDICATION

- ✓ Tab Methotrexate 15 mg P.O. once weekly
- ✓ Tab Hydroxychloroquine 200mg P.O. b.i.d.
- ✓ Tab Prednisolone 5mg P.O. b.i.d.

DISCUSSION

Patient appeared with symptoms of Cushing's syndrome (Anasarca, Moon shaped face, red thin skin, fever, body pain) .after the use of prednisolone for Rheumatoid Arthritis over 1 year duration, The patient was not taking any other medication which interact with prednisolone through cytochrome P450 to raise the cortisol level. The prednisolone substituted with other anti-inflammatory agents. The similar condition was observed in the case report of siddarama. R et. al. [1, 2]

CONCLUSION

Prednisolone was prescribed for Arthritis which induces Cushing's syndrome, the condition is reversible if drug is withdrawn, and prednisolone should be withdrawn in tapering manner over a period of 4 months.

THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTION

The Methotrexate is prescribed for long term use, as it is Dihydrofolate reductase inhibitor it may lead to the folic acid deficiency & anemia in the patient, the folic acid supplement should be prescribed on discharge medication.

LEARNING POINTS:

- ✓ Drug induced condition are preventable, Hence optimization of therapeutic regimen is very crucial in health care system.
- ✓ Switching to other class of drugs or withdraw of drug is best possible management of drug induced conditions.
- ✓ The clinical pharmacist has great opportunity to monitor the patient and identify the drug related problem and adopt the best practice to minimize them.^[6]

LIMITATIONS IN CASE REPORT:

- ❖ No any appropriate differential diagnosis was done to confirmatory identify whether the hypercortisolism is due to the drug or it might be due to the Adrenal-carcinoma or pheochromocytoma.
- ❖ There is no distinguishing between Cushing's syndrome or pseudo-hypercortisol levels.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS:

- ❖ Hb - Hemoglobin
- ❖ TLC - Total Leucocyte count
- ❖ RBC - Red Blood Cells
- ❖ PO - Per Oral
- ❖ IV - Intravenous
- ❖ Anti-CCP - anti citrullinated peptide

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